

The structure of Greek newspaper headlines: The case of *Eleftheron Vima* in the 1920s

Περίληψη

Η έρευνα αναλύει τους πρωτοσέλιδους τίτλους ελληνικών εφημερίδων, εστιάζοντας σε δεδομένα από την πρώτη δεκαετία της κυκλοφορίας της εφημ. *Ελεύθερον Βήμα*. Εξετάζονται τα ιδιαίτερα χαρακτηριστικά των τίτλων, τόσο σε επίπεδο γλωσσικής δομής (στο επίπεδο της παράλειψης λέξεων, της σειράς των όρων, της δομής των προτάσεων κτλ.), όσο και σε επίπεδο τυπογραφίας (μέγεθος, θέση, εναλλαγή πεζών/κεφαλαίων κτλ.). Το άρθρο αποτελεί το πρώτο μέρος μιας ευρύτερης διαχρονικής έρευνας η οποία επιχειρεί να διερευνήσει αφενός αν οι τίτλοι αποτελούν ένα ξεχωριστό κειμενικό είδος, αφετέρου τον τρόπο με τον οποίο εξελίχθηκαν στον άξονα του χρόνου.

1. Introduction

Although newspaper headlines, especially front-page headlines, are consistently the most widely read textual genre in the history of written texts (Mårdh 1980, 11), they still need to be studied more regarding their unique linguistic characteristics. For the English language, it has been argued that newspaper headlines may well constitute a separate textual genre, as they are characterized by a particular style and an idiosyncratic linguistic structure (see, for example, Borchmann 2024; Moncomble 2018; Aitchison 2006; Dor 2003). Regarding the (not so) well-studied headlines of American English, for example, typically function words such as articles are often omitted, and temporal reference is achieved more through lexical than grammatical means. For example, let us examine the following *New York Times* front page headline from the era of the American stock-market crash of late October 1929:

[1] Stocks collapse in 16,410,030-share day, but rally at close cheers brokers; bankers optimistic, to continue aid

In [1], we observe that:

- (i) The indefinite article *a* is omitted before the word *rally*,
- (ii) The definite article *the* is omitted before the word *close*,
- (iii) The auxiliary verb *is* is omitted in the phrase *bankers optimistic*
- (iv) The future tense is expressed by the infinitive (*to continue*)
- (v) The time reference is unusual, with the verbs in the present tense (*collapse*) even though the events happened in the past (here, a day ago).

This paper is an initial report on ongoing research to record the language and style of the headlines of Greek newspapers. We chose the front-page headlines

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because we noticed that the style and language of the front-page headlines differ from those of the inner pages. According to van Dijk (1988, 189), this difference probably arises from the fact that the front-page headlines and inside headlines seek to accomplish different purposes. Front-page headlines ‘sell’ the newspaper. Inner headings define what the reader is reading. Moreover, they are often the only information the reader ultimately retains.

Data for this research comes from the study of headlines accessible through the Historical Archive of the newspapers *To Vima* and *Ta Nea*. The Archive was chosen as the main source for our research both because of the quality and quantity of the data it provides (it covers a variety of Greek newspapers over a period of more than a century)¹ and because of the unrestricted access that was offered to us. The aim is to investigate and describe, on the one hand, the parameters that constitute the style and language of Greek front-page headlines on a synchronic level and, on the other hand, the changes that are observed in the structure and style of the headlines, on a diachronic level, throughout the period covered by the Historical Archive.

Greek newspaper	Period covered
Eleftheron Vima (Ελεύθερον Βήμα)	1922–1944
To Vima (Το Βήμα)	1945–today
Athenaika Nea (Αθηναϊκά Νέα)	1931–1945
Ta Nea (Τα Νέα)	1945–today

Table 1: The newspapers studied and the periods covered by each

In this research phase, we base our analysis on qualitative characteristics. To this end, in the context of the currently evolving research project, for each decade under consideration, an equal number of front-page headlines were selected in a statistically random manner, a database (index) was created, and the headlines in the index were studied in terms of their linguistic characteristics.

The Archive at this stage is partially digitized. It looks more like a ‘simple scan’ with OCR than a proper and complete digitization. The headlines are not automatically exportable. It requires page-by-page work: selecting headlines, typing them by hand, creating a database, tagging the database, studying the material, and drawing conclusions. Due to the large amount of work required, it was decided in the first phase to study the 1920s, and in subsequent work, we will proceed to a comparative analysis of the other decades up to the present day. The data for this study consists of 214 front page headlines selected in a statistically random manner. Due to the difficulty of the task and the lack of previous similar research for the Greek language, our present research is purely qualitative. In our subsequent work, we will also attempt a quantitative analysis.

2. Typographical features

Although, ultimately, we are interested in the linguistic side of analyzing the form of headlines, we cannot ignore their physical form as well. Thus, we start with a consideration of their typographical features.

The headline differs in form/spelling, language, and style from the main body of each article. It consists of one or more levels, which are usually formally

¹ For the covered period regarding *To Vima* and *Ta Nea*, see Table 1.

differentiated from each other and each of which performs different functions (cf. [2]):

[2] Hyper-headline	optional
Main headline	obligatory, may also exist as a stand-alone headline
Subheadline(s)	usually present but optional

The general aim of headlines, which also determines their form, is to convey the message quickly to the reader. The reader should be able to understand with minimum effort the basic information encoded in the headline. For this reason, each level in [2] is visually distinguished from the other, either by font size variations or straight horizontal lines. Each level may consist of complete sentences or elements smaller than a sentence. Depending on the gravity of the event, subheadlines can sometimes be as many as 6 or 7(!), as is typically reflected in the front-page headline of *Eleftheron Vima* from the 15.10.1927 issue, as quoted in [3]. Each line is usually autonomous both in terms of grammatical and syntactic information.

[3] <i>Hyper-headline</i>	ΤΟ ΠΑΓΚΟΣΜΙΟΝ ΠΝΕΥΜΑ 'the global spirit'
<i>Main headline</i>	Ο ΠΡΑΓΜΑΤΙΚΟΣ ΑΦΟΠΛΙΣΜΟΣ ΕΙΝΑΙ ΑΔΥΝΑΤΟΣ 'real disarmament is impossible'
<i>Subheadline(s)</i>	ΤΟ ΒΡΕΤΤΑΝΙΚΟΝ ΓΟΗΤΡΟΝ ΕΙΣ ΤΗΝ ΚΙΝΑΝ 'the British charm in China' Η ΜΑΣΚΑ ΤΩΝ ΕΥΡΩΠΑΙΩΝ ΙΔΕΟΛΟΓΩΝ 'the mask of European ideologists' Η ΑΞΙΑ ΤΩΝ ΣΤΟΛΩΝ ΚΑΙ ΤΩΝ ΕΞΟΠΛΙΣΜΩΝ 'the value of uniforms and equipment' Η ΝΑΥΜΑΧΙΑ ΤΗΣ ΠΙΟΥΤΛΑΝΔ ΚΑΙ Ο ΠΑΓΚΟΣΜΙΟΣ ΠΟΛΕΜΟΣ 'the naval battle of Jutland and the World War' Η ΣΤΑΘΕΡΟΤΗΣ ΤΗΣ ΕΙΡΗΝΗΣ 'the stability of peace' Η ΓΕΡΜΑΝΙΚΗ ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ ΚΑΙ Η ΕΠΙΣΤΡΟΦΗ ΤΟΥ ΚΑΪΖΕΡΜΙΑ 'the German democracy and the return of the Kaiserdom' ΣΥΝΕΝΤΕΥΞΙΣ ΜΕ ΤΟΝ ΜΠΕΡΝΑΡ ΣΩ 'interview with Bernard Shaw'

Eleftheron Vima 15.10.1927

2.1 Size

The font size of headlines varies, helping the reader to distinguish more easily between the building blocks of a long headline: hyper-headline – main headline – subheadline(s). Thus, the headline is usually more prominent than either the hyper-headline or subheadlines. Moreover, compared to each other, all the main headlines on the front page do not have the same font size. The size is usually proportional to the seriousness and drama of the event to which the headline refers.

2.2 Position

Throughout the decade under study, care is taken to ensure that the headlines of articles listed in adjacent columns are distinct in height on the front page. Obviously, this choice ensures that the articles are not in competition with each other. At the same time, this makes it even easier for readers to absorb the information.

2.3 Distinction between capital and non-capital letters

Throughout the 1920s, there was no distinction between capital and non-capital letters in front-page headlines. News and political headlines are strictly capitalized, a choice that is not maintained to this day as it changed in subsequent decades.

The only exception to this rule throughout the 1920s is some headlines that are written in non-capital letters but are always marked as to their subject. They usually correspond to articles on cultural issues and never current political affairs. A typical example is the front page of *Eleftheron Vima* of 15.7.1929, illustrated in Image 1. This peculiarity exists as early as 1928 and we could say that it was established in 1929.

Image 1: Front-page of *Eleftheron Vima* 15.7.1929

3. Linguistic features

3.1 Degree of conservatism

During the period under consideration, the so-called ‘Greek language question’, i.e., the parallel existence of two linguistic varieties, the colloquial Demotic, and the puristic Katharevousa, was in progress. Of these two varieties, Katharevousa was the official language of the State.

The interesting observation is that the headlines often seem to be written in less conservative language compared to the language of the article’s main body in question.² This feature is certainly compatible with the more general aim of making headlines attractive, understandable, and easier to process for the general readership. After all, the maximum possible attention of the public and the easiest possible transmission of information are the original functions of headlines.

A second hypothesis, which deserves further analysis, is that the less conservative language of the headlines in relation to the language of the article to which

² Interestingly, even the first Greek newspapers, that circulated during the 1821 Greek Revolution, adopted a learned linguistic style. We thank an anonymous reviewer who made this observation.

they correspond may be dictated by purely typographical factors. The forms in the Demotic are often of shorter length than their counterparts in the puristic language. Moreover, when it comes to headlines, the number of characters always matters.

3.2 Absence of words

Very often, words of reduced lexical information are missing from the headlines. Of these, the most frequent seems to be the absence of the verb 'to be' (see example [4]). Furthermore, the absence of the article is quite frequent, mainly the indefinite but sometimes also the definite, in structures where its absence is considered ungrammatical in Greek (see examples [5] and [6]).

- [4] Ο ΠΑΤΡΙΑΡΧΗΣ [είναι] ΠΡΟΣΦΥΓΕ ΕΙΣ ΤΟΝ ΑΘΩ
 'The Patriarch [is] a refugee to Athos'
Eleftheron Vima 15.7.1923
- [5] Ο ΧΑΡΙΓΚΤΩΝ ΕΠΕΣΤΡΕΨΕΝ ΕΚ [των] ΔΑΡΔΑΝΕΛΛΙΩΝ ΜΕΤΑ [την] ΕΠΙΘΕΩΡΗΣΙΝ
 'Harigton returned from [the] Dardanelles after [the] inspection'
Eleftheron Vima 15.1.1923
- [6] ΕΠΕΙΣΟΔΙΟΝ ΜΕΤΑΞΥ [των] ΑΜΕΡΙΚΑΝΩΝ ΚΑΙ [των] ΚΕΜΑΛΙΚΩΝ ΕΙΣ [την] ΠΡΙΓΚΗ-
 ΠΙΟΝ
 'An incident between [the] Americans and [the] Kemalists in [the] Prinkipos'
Eleftheron Vima 15.1.1923

In this last case, the absence of the article is notable with exceptionally high frequency in the prepositional structures: (a) *εις* + accusative, where 'movement to a place' is indicated; (b) *μετά* + accusative, where 'time' is indicated.

3.3 The dominance of nominal structures

In the language of headlines, throughout the 1920s, nominal structures predominated over verbal structures, whose presence was minimal. See the example given in [7] from the front page of *Eleftheron Vima* on 15.10.1924.

- [7] ΤΟΥΡΚΙΚΗ ΔΙΑΜΑΡΤΥΡΙΑ ΕΙΣ ΤΗΝ ΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΑΝ ΤΩΝ ΕΘΝΩΝ
 'Turkish protest to the League of Nations'
 Η ΕΥΘΥΝΗ ΔΙΑ ΤΑΣ ΣΥΝΕΠΕΙΑΣ ΤΟΥ ΑΓΓΛΙΚΟΥ ΤΕΛΕΣΙΓΡΑΦΟΥ
 'Responsibility for the consequences of the English telegram'
Eleftheron Vima 15.10.1924

Our corpus shows that this choice is not stable over time but changes throughout the following decades.

3.4 Constituents that are equal to or smaller than a sentence

As mentioned above, headlines are composed of different levels (hyper-headline – headline – subheadline), each of which has conceptual and syntactic autonomy. This autonomy is generally maintained from line to line. Indeed, each line may correspond to a construct equal to or (very often) shorter than the sentence. See the characteristic front-page headline of the *Eleftheron Vima* from the sheet of 15.1.1927, cited in [8].

[8]

‘THE DICTATOR SPEAKS
MY 24 HOURS
SILENCE’

3.5 Word Order

The word order is not fixed but varies from headline to headline. Thus, sometimes we find headlines with the word order V-S (see the first line in example [9]), sometimes with the word order S-V-O (see the second line in example [9]), and sometimes with the word order O-V-S (see the second line in example [10]).

- [9] ΑΠΕΙΛΕΙΤΑΙ Η ΣΕΡΒΟΚΡΟΑΤΙΚΗ ΣΥΜΦΩΝΙΑ
‘The Serbo-Croatian Agreement is threatened’
ΟΙ ΡΙΖΟΣΠΑΣΤΑΙ ΥΠΟΥΡΓΟΙ ΕΠΙΜΕΝΟΥΝ ΟΠΩΣ ΑΠΟΜΑΚΡΥΝΘΗ Ο Κ. ΣΤΕΠΑΝ ΡΑΔΙΤΣ
‘The radical ministers insist that Mr. Stepan Radic be removed’
Eleftheron Vima 15.4.1926

- [10] Η ΤΕΛΕΥΤΑΙΑ ΗΜΕΡΑ ΤΗΣ ΔΙΚΗΣ ΤΗΣ ΣΥΝΩΜΟΣΙΑΣ ΚΑΤΑ ΤΟΥ ΚΕΜΑΛ
‘The last day of the conspiracy trial against Kemal’
ΤΙ ΑΠΕΚΑΛΥΨΕΝ Η ΔΙΑΔΙΚΑΣΙΑ
‘What the procedure revealed’
Eleftheron Vima 15.7.1926

The factor that seems to have a decisive influence on the word order chosen each time is the information value of the term that is considered new. The new information comes first, while the already-known information comes after. In the first line of the headline quoted in [9], for example, the Serbo-Croatian Agreement is already known and has been discussed all along. Nevertheless, the fact that this agreement is ‘threatened’ is new information. Thus, the word order V-S is chosen.

3.6 Types of sentences regarding their content

The vast majority of headlines are declarative sentences (see example [11]). This finding is to some degree to be expected, given that the primary function of headlines is to convey one or more pieces of information.

- [11] ΑΠΟΚΑΛΕΙ “ΑΔΕΣΠΟΤΟΥΣ ΚΥΝΑΣ” ΤΟΥΣ ΑΞΙΩΜΑΤΙΚΟΥΣ, ΤΟΥΣ ΧΥΣΑΝΤΑΣ ΤΟ ΑΙΜΑ
ΤΩΝ ΕΙΣ ΤΑ ΠΕΔΙΑ ΤΩΝ ΜΑΧΩΝ
‘He calls the officers “stray dogs”, those who shed blood on the battlefields’
Eleftheron Vima 15.10.2022

To a lesser extent, one also finds interrogative sentences in the headlines. These sentences are often found without the punctuation expected for the genre, i.e., without a question mark at the end, as in example [12] (perhaps as if it were an implicit indirect question, i.e. “Αναρωτιόμαστε πώς ...”):

- [12] ΠΩΣ ΑΝΤΕΔΡΑΣΕΝ ΕΙΣ ΤΗΝ ΕΠΑΝΟΔΟΝ ΤΩΝ ΑΞΙΩΜΑΤΙΚΩΝ ΤΗΣ ΚΩΝΣΤΑΝΤΙΝΟΥΠΟ-
ΛΕΩΣ
‘How he reacted to the return of the officers of Constantinople’
Eleftheron Vima 15.10.2022

It is striking that imperative sentences are sometimes found in the material under study, which, given their prototypical function of giving commands, would not be expected in newspaper headlines, especially front-page ones. It is evident that this kind of headline is not stylistically neutral. On the contrary, they are strongly marked and constitute a decisive commentary/intervention on political developments. Consider, for example, the headlines [13] and [14], which are typical.

[13] ΜΗ ΤΟΡΠΙΛΙΖΕΤΕ ΤΟΥΛΑΧΙΣΤΟΝ ΤΑ ΘΕΜΕΛΙΑ ΤΟΥ ΚΡΑΤΟΥΣ
 'Do not torpedo, at the very least, the foundations of the state'
Eleftheron Vima 15.10.1929

[14] ΑΦΗΣΑΤΕ ΤΟΝ ΕΛΕΥΘΕΡΙΟΝ ΒΕΝΙΖΕΛΟΝ ΗΣΥΧΟΝ
 'Leave Eleftherios Venizelos in peace'
Eleftheron Vima 15.7.1924

Interestingly, neither of the above examples, [13] and [14], is an excerpt from a speech. The newspaper itself is the narrative voice. From this perspective, these examples are direct political intervention and a clear expression of a political position.

Finally, exclamatory sentences, such as those illustrated in examples [15] and [16], are not absent from our research material. This category of sentences usually indicates an emotional involvement of the writer or, more often, an attempt to achieve an emotional involvement of the reader.

[15] Ο ΒΕΝΙΖΕΛΟΣ ΚΥΒΕΡΝΑ!
 'Venizelos governs!'
Eleftheron Vima 15.7.1928

[16] ΠΛΟΥΤΩΝ, Ο ΝΕΟΣ ΠΛΑΝΗΤΗΣ ΠΟΥ ΕΒΑΠΤΙΣΕΝ ΕΝΑΣ ΕΛΛΗΝ!
 'Pluto, the new planet named by a Greek!'
Eleftheron Vima 15.7.1930

4. Discussion

This paper is the first part of a series of studies on the front-page headlines of Greek newspapers, the particular linguistic features that define them, and how these features have changed over the last 100 years. Although, for methodological reasons, this paper is limited to the study of the 1920s, the first decade of the life of the newspapers *Eleftheron Vima* and *Athenaika Nea*, it becomes evident that the front-page headlines display several characteristics that deviate from the standard variety of the language seen outside of headlines. Therefore, we argue that front page headlines in Greek should be considered as a separate textual genre, characterized by their conventions in relation to other textual genres and corresponding to their treatment as a distinct textual genre in English.

Indeed, it is particularly remarkable (and promising) that a first glance at the entire Historical Archive of the newspapers *To Vima* and *Ta Nea* shows that the conventions that characterize the headlines of the newspapers have not remained constant throughout time but are changing along the temporal axis. Further consideration of this observation through research taking in the decades after the 1920s will confirm, we expect, that headlines are a 'living' textual genre that (continues to) evolve (constantly). Headlines adapt – not always systematically – to the more general changes in the Greek language during the period under consideration (see also the evolving language issue in the 20th century, i.e., Mackridge 2016).

Finally, we realize that at least as far as English is concerned, ‘headline-ese’ may be considered to be a subtype together with other genres that show an acceptable degree of ellipsis, e.g., instructions on packages such as ‘Shake before serving’ on a bottle of salad dressing, meaning ‘Shake [this bottle] before serving [its contents]’, or the ellipsis one would see in telegrams or that one can see now in text messages. Thus, another extension of this research would be to see if the ellipsis in Greek headlines has parallels in other domains, raising the theoretical question of what it means for a particular ‘style’ to constitute a ‘genre’ in and of itself, and what sort of criteria are required to identify a ‘genre’ and to differentiate it from, or unite it with, other similar styles.

5. Future research

As noted above, this research is in progress and will continue with the study of the following decades in the coming months. On the one hand, it will be enriched with quantitative data regarding the extent of the observed changes. On the other hand, it will be extended to the recording of the characteristics of the headlines of the inside pages and the subsequent (qualitative and quantitative) comparative comparison of the characteristics of the inside page headlines with those of the front-page headlines.

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